

ISic1356

I.Sicily inscription 1356

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Found in the crypt of S. Marciano, in first half of 1722, under the SE
pilaster

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 61

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. □ ἐνθάδε κατάκιτε
2. ἡ τῆς μακαρίας μν
3. ἡμης Εὐλίβα μνήσε
4. τή σοι ὦ θε(ός) εἰς [αἰῶνα]

Apparatus

Text of IG with slight changes based on Kaibel's diplomatic transcription

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492970

EDCS 39101736

PHI 140860

Bibliography

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